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CHANGING BUSINESS APPROACHES OF STATE BANK OF INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Commercial banks provide a range of services to the whole community in many ways. Apart from the basic banking services such as deposits, loans and advances, banks have been traditionally rendering certain ancillary services to their customers such as remittances, demand drafts, mail transfers, and telegraphic transfers, sale and purchase of foreign exchange, locker facilities safe custody and safe deposit values, guarantee facilities sale of traveller's cheques, trustee and executor services etc. They act as bankers for the issue of ne capital. They help their customers in marketing of securities and send the dividends to the customer's account directly. Moreover, commercial banks undertake the payment of subscriptions, premix, rents etc. on behalf of their customers. Besides this, commercial banks undertake the issue of credit instruments like letters of credit, acceptance of bills of exchange and documents, acting as a referee as to the respectability and financial standing of customers and providing specialised advisory services to the customers. The study found that SBI is performing well and ahead of all commercial banks relating to service approach and getting better results.

KEYWORDS: Commercial Bank, SBI, Foreign Exchange, Remittance, Letter of Credit

INTRODUCTION :

The roots of the State Bank of India lie in the first decade of the 19th century, when the Bank of Calcutta, later renamed the Bank of Bengal, was established on 2 June 1806. The Bank of Bengal was one of three Presidency banks, the other two being the Bank of Bombay (incorporated on 15 April 1840) and the Bank of Madras (incorporated on 1 July 1843). All three Presidency banks were incorporated as joint stock companies and were the result of royal charters. These three banks received the exclusive right to issue paper currency till 1861 when, with the Paper Currency Act, the right was taken over by the Government of India. The Presidency banks amalgamated on 27 January 1921, and the re-organised banking entity took as its name Imperial Bank of India. The Imperial Bank of India remained a joint stock company but without Government participation.

Pursuant to the provisions of the State Bank of India Act of 1955, the Reserve Bank of India, which is India's central bank, acquired a controlling interest in the Imperial Bank of India. On 1 July 1955, the Imperial Bank of India became the State Bank of India. In 2008, the government of India acquired the Reserve Bank of India's stake in SBI so as to remove any conflict of interest because the RBI is the country's banking regulatory authority.

In 1959, the government passed the State Bank of India (Subsidiary Banks) Act, which made eight state banks associates of SBI. A process of consolidation began on 13 September 2008, when the State Bank of Saurashtra merged with SBI.

SBI has acquired local banks in rescues. The first was the Bank of Bihar (est. 1911), which SBI acquired in 1969, together with its 28 branches. The next year SBI acquired National Bank of Lahore (est. 1942), which had 24 branches. Five years later, in 1975, SBI acquired Krishnaram Baldeo Bank, which had been established in 1916 in Gwalior State, under the patronage of Maharaja Madho Rao Scindia. The bank had been the Dukan Pichadi, a small moneylender, owned by the Maharaja. The new bank's first manager was Jall N. Broacha, a

Parsi. In 1985, SBI acquired the Bank of Cochin in Kerala, which had 120 branches. SBI was the acquirer as its affiliate, the State Bank of Travancore, already had an extensive network in Kerala.

The State Bank of India and all its associate banks are identified by the same blue keyhole logo. The State Bank of India wordmark usually has one standard typeface, but also utilises other typefaces.

On October 7, 2013, Arundhati Bhattacharya became the first woman to be appointed Chairperson of the bank.

REVIEW LITERATURE:

D. K. Gupta & P. Gupta (2013) examined that Bank marketing is the aggregate of functions directed at providing services to satisfy customers' financial needs and wants more effectively and efficiently than the competitors keeping in view the organisational objectives of the bank. Public sector banks have a huge potential of experienced Human Resource and wide network spread all over India. It is revealed by the research that it is more the perception which is causing concern than the potential of PSBs. Public Sector banks, almost in all spheres of operations are having at par technology with peers. Optimum utilisation of technology is the theme of the problem. They should take immediate action in initiating system of sending in one lot the full package of account related information like debit card, internet banking ID and other related product to attract new and younger generation customers and retain its old clientele & work on improving the brand image on the security concern.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY :

1. To analyse the growth and development of commercial banks in India especially SBI with the help of several service approaches.
2. To study various changing business strategies of SBI with changing policies, norms and programmes of Govt. of India.
3. To study the overall changing service qualities of SBI, for retaining customer and improving customer satisfaction.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY :

Due to constraints of time and resources, the study may suffer from specific limitations. Some of these are mentioned here under so that the findings of the study may be analysed understood in a proper manner.

- The study is purely based on secondary data
- Results derived by using secondary data may not be appropriate
- Secondary data was taken from the annual reports of the SBI
- Secondary data may not show the actual position of the banks

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM :

After nationalisation of the banks, the SBI has made phenomenal progress both in quantitative and qualitative terms. The massive expansion in branches, the rapid growth in deposits and advances is quite phenomenal and unprecedented. It is high time to know whether after implementing the banking reforms, commercial banks have made immense progress or have narrowed down in this era. The role of SBI has increased a lot in order to provide better service and bring reforms in their policies as it involves greater interaction and interdependence among the various commercial banks of global economy. The business strategies of SBI have been more customer oriented. The focus is more on to be responsive by increasing overall efficiency of banks.

CORE OPERATIONS :

1. Interest rates :
Base rate was twice reduced during the year from 10% to 9.75% as on 20/9/2012, and then again to 9.70% as on 4/2/2013, the lowest amongst all banks and so pegged, to bring relief to all borrowers, particularly SME units, home loan borrowers, who continued to enjoy the lowest home loan interest rates, and commercial real estate accounts, which were aligned with the prevailing retail housing loans in terms of interest rates.
2. Product changes :
We have a great CASA franchise and savings bank accounts form the bulwark. The savings bank account is normally the first on-board facility availed by a customer and the referral point for all future services from the Bank. To preserve and enhance the value of our savings bank offering, your Bank introduced the following initiatives during the year :
 - Minimum balance in savings account was done away with.
 - The penalty on non-maintenance of Average Quarterly Balance stands withdrawn.
 - The inter-core transfer transactions have been made free, and cash deposit minimum charges were reduced from Rs. 25 to Rs. 10.
 - Introduction of Personal Accident Insurance Policy for all savings bank account holders at a nominal rate received tremendous response.
 - Proactively, providing CTS-2010 compliant multi- city chequebooks benefited all our customers.
3. e-Trade SBI :
A web-based portal, to enhance customer comfort and provide easy access to trade finance services, by enabling customers to lodge Letters of Credit, Bank Guarantees and Bills Collection/ negotiation requirements online from any corner of the world has been well received, with 1326 Corporates registered under e-Trade SBI as on 31.03.2013 and more than 11000 transactions per month through e-Trade platform.
4. e-VFS (Electronic Vendor Financing Scheme) & e-DFS (Electronic Dealer Financing Scheme) :
Fully automated and secured products, designed to ensure efficient management of working capital cycle of the corporates and sustained growth and profitability of business partners.
5. New Products launched :
The revised Kisan Credit Card scheme provides for comprehensive short term credit limit, assessed for 5 years with 10% step up every year, with inbuilt post harvest/household/consumption requirement, maintenance expenses of farm assets, Crop Insurance, Personal Accidental Insurance Scheme (PAIS), asset insurance and investment credit. In addition, loan account is operated through multi-delivery channels (PoS and ATMs) using the State Bank Kisan Cards.
Special campaigns were launched to accelerate agribusiness growth: 'Swarna Dhara Campaigns' for agri-gold loans was continued, with quarterly competitions and garnered Rs. 14,345 crores business.
6. ATM :
SBI has issued more than 11.00 crores Cards out of which around 8.54 crores Cards are transacting regularly on the ATMs. The State Bank Group's ATM operations run from two Switches. The BASE24 Switch has recently been upgraded and it can now handle close to 50,000 ATMs. The ATM footprint is being enlarged substantially through Brown Label ATMs which are being rolled

out as totally outsourced initiative under the guidance deployed for use by the executives for decision making. Campaign Management Tool has been implemented and campaigns through emails/ SMS have been launched by the various Business Units targeting customers under various segments. “Customer One view” (COV) has been developed for Corporate Account Group, Mid Corporate Group and Small and Medium Enterprise Accounts for better monitoring. Data Mining and Analytics are being performed in the areas of business development, Control, Performance and Profitability.

7. Improvement in employee productivity :

The large-scale recruitment of Gen-next employees in the officers as well as in the assistant grade have not only brought a far reaching attitudinal change among staff in their customer interface and services across the branches, it has also become a catalyst in enhancing / improving the productivity and efficiency of the employees, thereby resulting in increasing growth in business and profitability for the Bank. Consequently, both business per employee and also profit per employee went up significantly during the year.

FOLLOWING ANALYSIS HAS BEEN DONE IN ORDER TO SHOW ITS EFFICIENCY IN TERMS OF QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE ASPECT BY THE HELP OF CHANGING SERVICE APPROACHES

Graph-1

Source : SBI Annual Reports

From this table is clear how SBI is able to maintain its percentage from time to time by providing good service facilities in an increasing order. From time to time by providing good service in 2010-11 it was 10.69%, whereas it increased up to 12.92% in 2012-13. It only happens after changing its service approach towards the customers.

Graph -2

Source : SBI Annual Reports

This table shows about deposit and advances which is increasing from year to year. After facing so many competition is able to increase its deposit and advances. So it is clear how SBI is growing fast with new service approach .

Graph -3

Source : SBI Annual Reports

It shows return on asset that is net profit available after tax and dividends in relating to total assets. It is increasing from year to year which is a good sign for SBI.

Graph -5

Source : SBI Annual Reports

Graph -7

Source : SBI Annual Reports

How its deposits is increasing from time to time i.e., SBI is able to accept deposits from its public with providing optimum level service facilities.

Graph -4

Source : SBI Annual Reports

Net NPA is increasing from 2011-2013 continuously.

Graph -6

Source : SBI Annual Reports

Graph -8

Source : SBI Annual Reports

In housing loan aspect SBI also providing loans to its customers. So it shows customer relationship management and its maintenance. And that is fully influenced by the service factor.

Graph -9

Graph -10

Graph -11

Source : SBI Annual Reports

Table-1 : Financial Highlights for the Last ten years

	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
Liabilities										
Capital (₹ in crores)	526	526	526	526	631	635	635	635	671	684
Reserves & Surplus (₹ in crores)	19,705	23,546	27,118	30,772	48,401	57,313	65,314	64,351	83,280	98,200
Deposits (₹ in crores)	3,18,619	3,67,048	3,80,046	4,35,521	5,37,404	7,42,073	8,04,116	9,33,933	10,43,647	12,02,739
Borrowings (₹ in crores)	13,431	19,184	30,642	39,704	51,728	53,713	1,03,012	1,19,569	1,27,006	1,69,183
Other's (₹ in crores)	55,534	49,579	55,538	60,042	83,362	1,10,698	80,337	1,05,248	80,915	95,455
Total (₹ in crores)	4,07,815	4,59,883	4,93,870	5,66,565	7,21,526	9,64,432	10,53,414	12,23,736	13,35,519	15,66,261
Assets										
Investments (₹ in crores)	1,85,676	1,97,098	1,62,534	1,49,149	1,89,501	2,75,954	2,85,790	2,95,601	3,12,198	3,50,927
Advances (₹ in crores)	1,57,934	2,02,374	2,61,642	3,37,337	4,16,768	5,42,503	6,31,914	7,56,719	8,67,579	10,45,616
Other Assets (₹ in crores)	64,205	60,411	69,694	80,079	1,15,257	1,45,975	1,35,710	1,71,416	1,55,742	1,69,718
Total (₹ in crores)	4,07,815	4,59,883	4,93,870	5,66,565	7,21,526	9,64,432	10,53,414	12,23,736	13,35,519	15,66,261
Net Interest income (₹ in crores)	11,186	13,945	15,589	15,058	17,021	20,873	23,671	32,526	43,291	44,331
Provisions for NPA (₹ in crores)	3,703	1,204	148	1,429	2,001	2,475	5,148	8,792	11,546	11,368
Operating Result (₹ in crores)	9,553	10,990	11,299	10,000	13,108	17,915	18,321	25,336	31,574	31,082
Net Profit Before Taxes (₹ in crores)	4,971	6,522	6,906	7,625	10,439	14,181	13,926	14,954	18,483	19,951
Net Profit (₹ in crores)	3,681	4,305	4,407	4,541	6,729	9,121	9,166	8,265	11,707	14,105
Return on Average Assets (%)	0.94	0.99	0.89	0.84	1.01	1.04	0.88	0.71	0.88	0.91
Return on Equity (%)	18.19	18.10	15.47	14.24	17.82	15.07	14.04	12.84	14.36	15.94
Expenses to Income (₹) (Operating Expenses to total Net Income)	49.18	47.83	58.70	54.18	49.03	46.62	52.59	47.60	45.23	48.51
Profit Per Employee (₹ in 000)	177	207	217	237	373	474	446	385	531	645
Earnings Per Share (₹)	69.94	81.79	83.73	86.10	126.62	143.77	144.37	130.16	184.31	210.06
Dividend Per Share (₹)	11.00	12.50	14.00	14.00	21.50	29.00	30.00	30.00	35.00	41.50
SBI Share (Price on NSE) (₹)	605.85	654.80	968.50	994.45	1,600.25	1,067.10	2,078.20	2,765.30	2,096.35	2,072.75
Dividend Payout Ratio (%)	15.72	15.28	16.72	16.22	20.18	20.19	20.78	23.05	20.06	20.12
Capital Adequacy Ratio (%)										
Basel- I (%)	13.53	12.45	11.88	12.34	13.54	12.97	12	10.69	12.05	11.22
Tier I	8.34	8.04	9.36	8.01	9.14	8.53	8.46	6.93	8.50	8.23
Tier II	5.19	4.41	2.52	4.33	4.40	4.44	3.54	3.76	3.55	2.99
Basel- II (₹ in crores)						85,393	90,975	98,530	1,16,325	1,29,362
(%)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	14.25	13.39	11.98	13.86	12.92
Tier I (₹ in crores)						56,257	64,177	63,901	82,125	94,947
(%)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	9.38	9.45	7.77	9.79	9.49
Tier II (₹ in crores)						29,136	26,798	34,629	34,200	34,415
(%)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	4.87	3.94	4.21	4.07	3.43
Net NPA to Net Advances (%)	3.48	2.65	1.88	1.56	1.78	1.79	1.72	1.63	1.82	2.10
Number of Domestic Branches	9,039	9,102	9,177	9,231	10,186	11,448	12,496	13,542	14,097	14,816
Number of Foreign Branches/ Offices	54	54	70	83	84	92	142	156	173	186

Source : SBI Annual Reports

It shows its financial stability from 2003-04 to 2012-13. Where it shows its financial position. In every aspect SBI is able to maintain its percentage of efficiency by providing the new innovative service approaches.

FINDINGS & CONCLUSION :

The study found that the SBI increasing its overall performance inspite of so many hurdles. Every commercial bank is providing some specific service facilities but SBI is providing new service facility with innovative approach. During the stiff competition period also the SBI is able to maintain its rank position among all the commercial bank. No doubt the SBI is facing so many constraints when new private sector and foreign bank introduce their new business strategy and policy to capture Indian monetary market after bank reform. The following points have been covered by SBI exclusively in order to achieve better result.

- SBI is providing modern equipment and also very cautious towards physical facilities.
- It is giving stress on reliability by keeping the promises made earlier.
- SBI is showing its sincerity by solving the problem of customer and providing error free transactions.
- It is also following the time bound process and providing the exact time about the service performance.
- SBI is also paying individual attention and also securing transactions of individual.

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- It creates confidence among customers by providing prompt service.
- It also answer the question presented by the customer smoothly with counseling.

From the above source analysis the study found that SBI is not only financial strong but also provides high degree service facilities for that is able to maintain its quantitative and qualitative aspect. Hence on the basis of above analysis one can know how SBI is increasing its efficiency by changing its service approaches towards the customer, industry etc.

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